

tunES

D4.1 Improved Good Practice Guidance

Methodology Guidance - Based on 'Better Regulation' Toolbox 2023

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Version:3.0, Status: Final, Dissemination Level: Public, Work Package: WP4
Submission Date: 27.03.2026

Co-funded by the
European Union

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Content

Better Regulation Guideline

Problem and Objective Trees

Stakeholder Consultation

Policy Options

Impact Assessment

Better Regulation Guideline

The BRG is a collection of tools and methods for evidence-based, transparent and inclusive policy-making.

Better Regulation Guideline (BRG) Overview

The BRG is a very advanced approach to policy making

BRG - A EUROPEAN FRAMEWORK TO POLICY MAKING

- ▶ A working document for Commission staff (revised on 3 November 2021)
- ▶ A companion resource - the Better Regulation Toolbox (20 July 2023)

BRG OVERVIEW

Objectives of Better Regulation:

Ensure EU policymaking is based on evidence

Involve citizens, businesses and stakeholders in the decision-making process

Make EU laws

69 tools, >600 pages

Evidence-based

Transparent

Policy-making

Inclusive

Problem & Objective Trees

1unES 11

Problem Tree

This section describes the steps to verify the existence of a problem or a need for policy measures implementation. The information help to identify the problem, its drivers and consequences.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #13 How to analyse problems

1unES 12

Extension of the problem

This section describes the steps to verify if the need for a possible policy initiative is going to persist. It will help to estimate the scale of the problem.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #13 How to analyse problems

1unES 14

Turning the Problem Tree into an Objective Tree

This section describes the steps to link the problems and their drivers to the policy options. The proposed tool helps to set your objectives.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool # 15 How to set objectives

Problem Tree

This section describes the steps to verify the existence of a problem or a need for policy measures implementation. The information help to identify the problem, its drivers and consequences.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #13 How to analyse problems

Problem Tree – Main components

The Problem Tree is the first step in a series of analytic approaches to resolve a policy issue

Problem Tree – Motivation

The core result of a Problem Tree is focusing on the most important issue and understand the causality

PROBLEM TREE SERVES TO

Identify the Problem

Analyse its Drivers

Identify who is affected and involved

LATER TO DEFINE THE BASELINE AND PREPARE IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Estimate the scale of the Problem

Assess the likelihood that
the Problem will persist

Problem Tree – How to? – General

The Problem Tree is an exercise in finding the core issue and thereby limiting the scope of later analysis

► Strategies to consider:

- Depict graphically the relations between drivers, problems and their consequences.
- Avoid complexity (do not record to granular detail or fringe scenarios).
- Brainstorm: List all problems related to the main theme.
- Reduce: Are multiple items actually stating the same?
- Focus/Verify: Which items have the largest impact / relevance at the earliest stage?

► Define the problem: an **existing negative situation**.

- **Status quo:** Describe the current situation. What findings did the relevant evaluations and fitness checks show?
- **Scale:** What is the issue that may require action? What is the size or scale of the problem? Is there a cross-border dimension?
- **Actors:** What and whose behaviour would need to change and why?
- **Related issues:** What is linked to the pursuit of general objectives? International issues, lack of coherence with EU development objectives, etc.
- **Consequences:** What are the economic, social, environmental and other consequences?
- **Persistence:** How likely is the problem to persist? How will the problem evolve generally in the absence of EU action?

Problem Tree – How to? – Drivers

Policy measures will aim at removing Drivers (and thereby the Problem and the Consequences)

SIMPLY REMOVING THE PROBLEM DOES NOT SOLVE IT

**If the Drivers remain unchanged,
they Problem will reappear**

HOW TO FIND DRIVERS

Rule of 5 Whys: ask 'why' 5 times to get to the root driver(s) of a Problem

- ▶ Lead / example questions you could ask:
 - What are the main drivers?
 - What is the source of drivers? (people's behaviour or some other source)
 - What are the market failures, regulatory failures, or behavioural biases, which are responsible for the observed problem?
 - What evidence is there available?
 - What are the drivers outside of your usual action radius?
- ▶ Example:

Problem	Traffic congestion in a city
Why?	Too many vehicles on the road
Why?	People prefer private cars
Why?	Public transportation system is unreliable
Why?	Insufficient investment in public transport
Why?	Funding prioritisation

Problem Tree – Example – First steps

Describe the negative situation as of today

ASSESS THE SITUATION TODAY

Extension of the problem

This section describes the steps to verify if the need for a possible policy initiative is going to persist. It will help to estimate the scale of the problem.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #13 How to analyse problems

Problem Tree – Example

The Problem Tree enables first calculations of the baseline

THE PROBLEM TODAY

THE PROBLEM IN THE FUTURE TREE

- ▶ The existence of a problem does not justify action
 - Some problems may disappear / decline in size (i.e. do not require action)
 - Some problems “feel” large but have not been quantified
- ▶ The exercise of modelling the problem into the future also sets the benchmark (i.e. baseline) against which the policy options (actions) are to be assessed against

Estimate the scale of the Problem

Thousands of deaths from air pollution in 2020.

Assess the likelihood that the Problem will persist

In 20 years, bicycles and public transport will replace cars

Persistence

Assess the likelihood that the problem will persist

Complement with long-term scenarios – plausible consistent pictures of the future

What would happen without any action? (i.e. baseline)

Consider more complete implementation of existing policy

Any way current policy could be better implemented / enforced?

Consider adopted (but not yet implemented) policy changes

Would maybe other upcoming policy solve the problem (i.e. not additional policy necessary)?

Scale of the Problem

Show the relevance of the problem

Collect evidence to show the importance and scale of the problem

How will the consequences add up over time?

Provide the context: describe size of market, structure, affected businesses

Describe who is adversely affected by the consequences and which «damage» (e.g. economic, social) this might imply.

Turning the Problem Tree into an Objective Tree

This section describes the steps to link the problems and their drivers to the policy options. The proposed tool helps to set your objectives.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool # 15 How to set objectives

Objective Tree | Theory of Change

We then search for the desirable features of policy options to change baseline and achieve (positive) impact

Theory of Change

Translate objectives and drivers into a structured Theory of Change

Rationale	Process	Outcome
Maps out cause-effect relationships	Outline each action, output, and interim outcome that links drivers to objectives	Shows how actions lead to outcomes, creating a coherent impact pathway
Considers external factors	Note assumptions and factors that may impact each step along the pathway	Supports evidence-based adjustments for success
Provides a structured intervention	Visualise the step-by-step causal pathway from drivers to impact	Fosters shared understanding and support
Ensures stakeholder alignment	Create a flow diagram to show the cause-effect chain, from activities to outcomes	Supports collaboration and agreement on goals and steps
	Review pathway and assumptions to confirm alignment and transparency	

S.M.A.R.T. objectives

Use the SMART criteria to set your specific objectives

Specific

Precise and concrete, no varying interpretations

Measurable

A defined desire future state to allow verification

Achievable

Realistic and properly justified

Relevant

Directly linked to the problem and its drivers

Time-Bound

Related to a fixed date

National Stakeholder Engagement

tunes 21

Overview

This section provides overview on the stakeholders' engagement process and describes stakeholder identification process.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #52 Consultation strategy

This slide features a teal header with the 'tunes' logo and slide number '21'. Below the header is a white section with the title 'Overview' in bold. A light green section contains a descriptive paragraph. A darker green section at the bottom lists the 'Better Regulation Toolbox' tool used. The slide is decorated with a light blue wave pattern at the bottom.

tunes 22

Survey

This section provides overview on the purpose of a survey and the steps for its implementation.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #53 Conducting consultation activities

This slide features a teal header with the 'tunes' logo and slide number '22'. Below the header is a white section with the title 'Survey' in bold. A light green section contains a descriptive paragraph. A darker green section at the bottom lists the 'Better Regulation Toolbox' tool used. The slide is decorated with a light blue wave pattern at the bottom.

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Interviews

This section provides overview on the purpose of interviews and the steps for their implementation.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #53 Conducting consultation activities

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Overview

This section provides overview on the stakeholders' engagement process and describes stakeholder identification process.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #52 Consultation strategy

Stakeholder Engagement Process Overview

Collaborative shaping of policy from data collection to implementation

TUNES WORKPLAN

Mapping stakeholders

Answer these questions from the BRG Toolbox #52 to identify preliminary stakeholders

The 'six tests for stakeholder identification'

Test 1. Who is directly impacted?

Test 2. Who is indirectly impacted?

Test 3. Who is potentially impacted?

Test 4. Whose help is needed to make it work?

Test 5. Who thinks they know about the subject?

Test 6. Who will show an interest in the subject?

Stakeholder Engagement

Example of stakeholders types to be targeted

TYPES OF NATIONAL STAKEHOLDER

Responsible local authorities and National Authorities

Associations of industry or professionals and communities of experts

Civil society organisations

Academic organisations

Companies and business representatives

Financial organisations interested in using EPCs to signal funding opportunities for energy renovations

Survey

This section provides overview on the purpose of a survey and the steps for its implementation.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #53 Conducting consultation activities

Surveys – Purpose as in BRG

Surveys drive the refinement of policy challenges and goals by integrating diverse stakeholder insights

Collecting critical data and insights from a wide range of stakeholders

Gathering feedback on the current state of EPC and SRI instruments

Identifying challenges and opportunities for improvement

Validation of the Problem Tree and later the Objective Tree

Evidence Collection

Survey implementation

Methodology Guidance | National Stakeholder Engagement

Interviews

This section provides overview on the purpose of interviews and the steps for their implementation.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #53 Conducting consultation activities

Interviews - purpose

Interviews explain the national context and uncover policy gaps, informing robust policy development

Interviews - implementation

Interviews are implemented in the following steps

Policy Options

tunES 32

Overview

This section provides overview on policy development process and policy options.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #16 How to Identify Policy Options

tunES 34

Baseline

This section describes the steps to create a policy baseline.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #60 Baselines

tunES 36

Compiling policy options

This section describes how to assemble a wide variety of policy options in addition to the baseline.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #16 How to Identify Policy Options

tunES 42

Using the tunES EPBD Excel to Identify Baseline and Policy Options

This section describes the Excel Tool as an instrument for developing policy options.

Overview

This section provides overview on policy development process and policy options.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #16 How to Identify Policy Options

Understanding Policy Options in BRG

Policy options explore diverse interventions for effective policy-making

Policy options are combinations or packages of policy measures designed to address identified problems and achieve policy objectives

Policy options explore different possible interventions to be explored through the impact assessment

Baseline

This section describes the steps to create a policy baseline.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #60 Baselines

Constructing Baseline

Baseline is essential for understanding the current state of affairs and predicting future developments in the absence of new interventions

Steps to Construct a Baseline

Define the policy area: identify policy area, problems, objectives, and stakeholders

Describe current situation: collect quantitative (statistics, reports) and qualitative (feedback, case studies) data

Review existing policies and their impacts; predict their evolution

Use historical data to forecast future developments under status quo

Define key variables like economic indicators, health outcomes, environmental, and social metrics

Validate baseline scenario with stakeholder input on current and future states

Document baseline scenario in detail

Compiling policy options

This section describes how to assemble a wide variety of policy options in addition to the baseline.

Better Regulation Toolbox used: Tool #16 How to Identify Policy Options

Assembling Policy Options

From the remaining measures several policy options with varying ambitions are created

Baseline	PO1 (Basic)	PO2 (Advanced)	PO3 (Comprehensive)
No interventions	Basic Measures -	Advanced Measures + Some Basic Measures	Comprehensive Measures + Advanced/Basic Measures
	Simplest form of intervention with minimal changes	More significant changes involving regulatory and non- regulatory measures	Extensive interventions with significant regulatory overhauls
	Less intrusive, low cost, limited resources	More comprehensive, higher costs, robust intervention	Highly ambitious, resource- intensive, coordinated actions
	Examples: EPC Validity 10 years EPC for sales only	Examples: EPC Validity 5 years (i.e. <10) EPC for sales + rent	Examples: Dynamic EPC EPC Validity 5 years (same) EPC for sales + rent (same)
	BRG Examples: Information campaigns, minor regulatory adjustments, voluntary guidelines, or enhanced enforcement of existing regulations	New regulatory frameworks, substantial amendments to existing laws, combined regulatory and non-regulatory measures	Full legislative packages, major regulatory reforms, extensive new programmes with supporting measures like subsidies or incentives

Framework and Definitions

To ensure policy options cover all possible measures and provide a clarity, a tree-like structure is helpful

Method for collection of measures

tunES deployed a three step process to collect measures for policy option development

Discarding Policy Measures at an Early Stage

This step ensures that only the most viable and effective options are considered for further analysis and implementation

Outlining the assembled policy options

It is necessary to detail each policy option to identify the impacts of alternative options and ensure transparency

How to describe policy options?

Differentiate them based on objectives, avoiding vague descriptions

Specify how, by whom, and when each option will be implemented and monitored

Identify any additional actions needed

Provide specific actions for stakeholders to support impact analysis (benefits, costs, etc.)

Highlight differences from the baseline and other options

Theory of Change: Show how each policy option is expected to lead to the desired results, step by step

Using the tunES EPBD Excel to Identify Baseline and Policy Options

This section describes the Excel Tool as an instrument for developing policy options.

Structure of the Excel Tool

The Excel Tool collects measures in a structured way and contains following elements

Functionality of the Excel Tool

The Tool provides data filtering and summary functions for comprehensive analysis of measures and policy options

Search

- (Select All)
- BRP
- BRP-Content
- Database
- Database-Access
- EPC Content
- EPC Content - Recommendations
- EPC Design
- EPC Front Page
- EPC Method
- EPC Renewal
- EPC Scope
- EPC Triggers

Apply filters to narrow down the scope. Filters are in every column. Multiple filters can be used together.

SUMMARY	x	x	x	x	Z99	All	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	Q99	BRP-Content	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	P99	BRP	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	O99	Integration	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY		x	x		N99	Database-Access	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	M99	Database	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY		x	x		K99	EPC Content	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY	x	x	x	x	L99	EPC Content - Recom	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	J99	EPC Front Page	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY	x	x	x		I99	EPC Design	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY	x			x	H99	EPC-Enforcement	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY	x			x	G99	EPC-Experts	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY	x	x			F99	EPC-Display	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY		x		x	E99	EPC Renewal	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	D99	EPC Triggers	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY	x				C99	Uptake	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	C99	Uptake-SRI	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY	x	x			B99	EPC Method	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY		x			A99	EPC Scope	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	R99	SRI Method	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.
SUMMARY				x	S99	SRI Trigger	As a result at least the following number of fields is ticked.

The summary calculates the total number of measures used across the Baseline, Basic, Advanced, and Comprehensive and Reject columns, as well as the count of measures from specific pillars within these columns.

First: Identify the baseline

Selected measures which describe the status quo

Select all baseline measures with “x”

The selection will help to document a baseline scenario and exclude the measures for further steps

Pillar	Measure	EPBD	Baseline	Basic P01	Advanced PO2.1	Comprehensive PO3.1
EPC Scope	Certification is required for the entire non-residential building	-				
EPC Scope	Certification is required for each individual non-residential building unit	-				
EPC Scope	Certification is required for the entire residential building	-				
EPC Scope	Certification is required for each individual residential building unit	-				
EPC Scope	Certification of building units may be based on the whole building	19(11)a - o				
EPC Scope	Certification of building units may be based on the assessment of another representative building unit with the same energy-	19(11)b - o				
EPC Scope	Certification for single-family houses may be based on the assessment of other representative/similar building.	19(12) - o				
EPC Scope	The validity of EPCs does not exceed 10 years for all building types	19(13) - m				
EPC Scope	The validity of EPCs does not exceed 5 years	Example for other				
EPC Scope	Exemption: worship or religious activities	20 (6)+5(3b) - o				
EPC Scope	Exemption: temporary buildings	20 (6)+5(3c) - o				
EPC Scope	Exemption: industrial sites	20 (6)+5(3c) - o				

Policy Measures included in the Baseline

Second: Define policy options and view them

After selecting ambitions, the tool gives an overview by applying filters

For all measures not in the baseline, select ambition or rejection of measures with “x”

Use the filter function to get an overview of the desired policy option or a baseline

The overview will allow to describe the key aspects of retained policy options for reporting and impact assessment

Applying filters to policy components and pillars clarifies how the chosen policy option addresses each filtered component or pillar.

Applying filters to Policy Options shows which Policy Measures are included in the respective column

U	U	I	S	ID	Pillar	Measure	EPBD	Baseline	P01	PO2.1	PO3.1	Reject
x					A01 EPC Scope	Certification is required for the entire non-residential building	-					
x					A02 EPC Scope	Certification is required for each individual non-residential building unit	-					
x					A03 EPC Scope	Certification is required for the entire residential building	-					
x					A04 EPC Scope	Certification is required for each individual residential building unit	-					
x					A05 EPC Scope	Certification of building units may be based on the whole building	19(11)a - o					
x					A06 EPC Scope	Certification of building units may be based on the assessment of another representative building unit with the same energy-relevant characteristics in the same building	19(11)b - o					
x					A07 EPC Scope	Certification for single-family houses may be based on the assessment of other representative/similar building.	19(12) - o					

Checklist: Steps to select measures in tool

Energy Agencies are required to go through each measure and categorise them

Selections are made by typing 'x'

Start by identifying the baseline measures (the ones that are already in place in your country)

Reject measures that are not feasible at an early stage and explain why in "notes" column

Filter out baseline and rejected measures and specify if the remaining are Basic, Advanced, or Comprehensive
They can belong to one or a combination, depending on the policy options

Pillar	Measure	EPBD	Baseline	P01	PO2.1	PO3.1	Reject
Uptake-SRI	Participate in National Testing Phases for SRI	Art 15(2) - v					
Uptake-SRI	Participate in a Non-Committal National Test Phase for SRI	Art 15(3) - v					
Uptake-SRI	Clarify the Complementary Role of SRI in Relation to Energy Performance C	Art 15(3) - v					
Uptake-SRI	Conduct awareness campaigns to help building owners and occupants unc	Art 15, R56 - v					
Uptake-SRI	Engage stakeholders in the co-creation of SRI assessment tools and service-						
Uptake-SRI	Establish stakeholder dialogue to support SRI-related public funding schen-						

Measures sorted into Basic, Advanced, and Comprehensive Policy Options

Impact Assessment

Impact assessment process

We implement the assessment in three stages

QUANTITATIVE (PART OF MULTI-CRITERIA)

We assess the quantifiable effectiveness and efficiency.

Example: energy savings and costs

We use the Excel Model tool to calculate indicators.

It utilises national data and allow for national “weights” (i.e. the factor in “theory of change”).

BRG Tool #63

QUALITATIVE + VALUES FROM MODEL

We assess advantages and disadvantages of policy options for significant impact areas against baseline.

Example: What does PO1, PO2, PO3 do for digitalisation, air quality, CO2.

This helps to refine the Policy Options (if one has no advantages, it should not exist this way) + provides input on what **quantification** is needed.

BRG Tool #30, 36

“FULL” MULTI-CRITERIA RANKING

We write up assessment for effectiveness, efficiency, proportionality and coherence.

We score the policy options - with baseline equal 0 – from -3 to +3.

The best ranked option is our preferred option.

(+ update of step 2)

BRG Tool #62

Stage 1 – Quantitative - IA Model

CBA is implemented as Excel tool: setting of weights and the result across a wide range of indicators

SHEET: SETTINGS

For entering values

The summary over baseline and all options

SHEETS: BASELINE/PO1/PO2...

Calculations are automatic

No action

3	4	5
		MASTER 2025
Number/Dwellings/Floor area of today's (not demolished) building		
Share of SMALL buildings in building stock		
Share of MEDIUM building in building stock		
Share of LARGE building in building stock		
Av. number of dwellings in SMALL buildings		
Av. number of dwellings in MEDIUM buildings		
Av. number of dwellings in LARGE buildings		
Total number of Dwellings in Residential Buildings	Sum	

▶ Baseline values

▶ Example

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Variables	NPV Result			2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
		<u>Total energy consumption of...</u>		Based on floor area				
100		...unrenovated SMALL buildings (GWh)		975	966	957	949	940
100		unrenovated MEDIUM buildings (GWh)		1,500	1,487	1,473	1,460	1,446
100		...unrenovated LARGE buildings (GWh)		1,000	991	982	973	964
CALCULATED USED								
		...all unrenovated buildings		3,475	3,444	3,413	3,381	3,350
		...renovated SMALL buildings (GWh)		0	6	13	19	26
		...renovated MEDIUM buildings (GWh)		0	5	10	16	21
		...renovated LARGE buildings (GWh)		0	3	7	10	14
		...all renovated buildings		0	15	30	46	61
		...all undemolished Residential Buildings (GWh)		3,475	3,459	3,443	3,427	3,411
		Share of original energy consumption		100%	100%	99%	99%	98%

Stage 1 – Quantitative - IA Model

SHEET: COLLECTION

Baseline is zero – no changes

Comparison of results for each PO against baseline

ROW		Baseline	PO1	PO2.1	PO2.2	PO2.3	PO3	Baseline	PO1	PO2.1	PO2.2	PO2.3	PO3
Costs for building owners (without any subsidies)								Against baseline (baseline should always be zero)					
Residential Buildings													
176	NPV-corrected EPC costs (million €)	24.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-24.68	-24.68	-24.68	-24.68	-24.68
281	NPV-corrected BRP subsidy costs (million €)	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04
Non-Residential Buildings													
228	NPV-corrected EPC costs (million €)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
321	NPV-corrected BRP costs (million €)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
360	NPV-corrected SRI costs (million €)	0.00	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05

Stage 2 - Qualitative

Think and write impacts through

STEP 1 – PICK SIGNIFICANT IMPACT AREAS (BRG)

- ▶ Impact Areas (BRG Tool #18)
 - Social
 - Economic
 - Environmental (BRG Tool #36)

Impact on	Economic	Social	Environmental
Climate			✓
Quality of natural resources (water, soil, air etc.)			✓
Biodiversity, including flora, fauna, ecosystems, and landscapes			✓
Animal welfare			✓
Working conditions, job standards and quality		✓	
Public health & safety and health systems		✓	
Culture		✓	
Governance, participation, and good administration		✓	
Education and training, education, and training systems	✓	✓	
Conduct of business	✓		
Position of SMEs ²⁰⁰	✓		
Administrative burdens on business	✓		
Sectoral competitiveness, trade, and investment flows	✓		
Functioning of the internal market and competition	✓		
Public authorities (and budgets)	✓		
Sustainable consumption and production	✓		✓
Efficient use of resources (renewable & non-renewable)	✓		✓
Land use	✓		✓
The likelihood or scale of environmental risks	✓		✓
Employment	✓	✓	
Income distribution, social protection, and social inclusion (of particular groups)	✓	✓	
Technological development / digital economy	✓	✓	
Consumers and households	✓	✓	
Capital movements; financial markets; stability of the euro	✓	✓	
Property rights; intellectual property rights	✓	✓	
Territorial impacts (specific (types of) regions and sectors)	✓	✓	✓
Innovation (productivity and resource efficiency); research (academic and industrial)	✓	✓	✓
Fraud, crime, terrorism, and security, including hybrid threats	✓	✓	✓
Resilience, technological sovereignty, open strategic autonomy, security of supply	✓	✓	✓
Transport and the use of energy	✓	✓	✓
Food safety, food security and nutrition	✓	✓	✓
Waste production, generation, and recycling	✓	✓	✓
Third countries, developing countries, and international relations	✓	✓	✓
Sustainable development	✓	✓	✓
Fundamental rights	✓	✓	✓

* - The 'tick' denotes an indicative dominant category of impact

STEP 2 – EXPLAIN AND DESCRIBE THE IMPACT OF EACH PO

- ▶ Simple logical reasoning. “What happens if I do this ...”
- ▶ Each impact area has three sections (example at the next slide):
 - Introduction
 - Assessment
 - Identify the nature of the impact (who, what) in this area.
 - Describe whether and how much each is affected by each policy options.
 - You can include graphics for illustration.
 - Conclusion
 - For baseline and each PO list advantages and disadvantages which MUST follow from / exist in text above.
- ▶ We do NOT identify the preferred option.
- ▶ The reader can pick each impact area and understand what each PO does to it.
 - Any party could read this selectively...
 - ...but everything is covered so there is no hiding and cherry picking of evidence.

Stage 2 - Qualitative - Example

Structure and examples of the text

ASSESSMENT

Description of Impact area

Environmental impacts are changes in the state of the environment due to ...

Assessment of Policy Options

Compared to the baseline, Policy Option X makes moderate/extensive contributions ...

Achieved objective(s)

Avoided GHG emissions are ...

CONCLUSION

Summary of the positive impacts and shortcomings against the baseline

Table 2. Qualitative Assessment: Summary of Key Environmental Impacts

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Baseline		
PO1		
PO2		
PO3		

Stage 3 – Multi-criteria ranking

As part of the assessment, we deploy qualitative and quantitative tools as part of multi-criteria assessment (BRT #62)

Effectiveness

- ▶ Qualitative assessment (#30, #36) how well a policy option achieves each specific and general objective ...
- ▶ ... supported by quantitative data from the CBA tool (e.g. energy saved)

Efficiency

- ▶ Quantitative assessment of all effects over time
 - Relative to the baseline (i.e. set to zero)
 - Accumulated over time
 - Where possible monetized and net present value corrected

CBA Tool (BRT #63)

Coherence

- ▶ Qualitative assessment of how well the policy option interacts or contributes to and does not contradict or undermine other relevant legislation with the same objectives.

Proportionality

- ▶ Qualitative assessment to what degree a policy option is doable for all stakeholder groups...
- ▶ ... supported by quantitative data from the CBA tool (e.g. administrative burden or new compliance costs)

National Report

All methodological steps are collected and described in a report to be disseminated on MS level

Structure of National Report

Description of each step of analysis and assessment

STRUCTURE

- ▶ Current situation and objectives
 - Problem definition
 - Policy objectives
- ▶ What policy Options are available?
 - Policy Measures
 - Baseline
 - Description of Policy Options
- ▶ Theory of Change
- ▶ Impact Assessment
 - Quantitative assessment
 - Qualitative assessment
 - Multi-criteria analysis
- ▶ Roll-out pathway

DISSEMINATION

- ▶ Energy Agencies are in charge of the National Reports
- ▶ All files are shared with the European Commission, DG ENER, CINEA
- ▶ The decision on publication of the Reports remains with the Energy Agencies and Ministries
- ▶ We encourage publication under tunES, as agency or fully officially.
 - Translation is a good way to make the results accessible.

Results of tunES project

Summary of analysis conducted by seven
Energy Agencies

Policy Options overview

Distribution of policy measures across three levels of ambition (summary)

BASIC: MANDATORY EPBD REQUIREMENTS

Layout and content of EPC

National database,
central information website

Awareness campaign

Experts' certification system

Voluntary BRP

ADVANCED: + OPTIONAL EPBD REQUIREMENTS

Deeper renovation advice

Subsidies for vulnerable households

One-stop-shops

Voluntary BRP

Introduction and integration of SRI

SRI training

COMPREHENSIVE: + ADDITIONAL MEASURES

Integrated building passports and
real-time monitoring

Comprehensive financial
mechanisms

Info portals with detailed data

Mandatory BRP

Mandatory SRI

Interoperability between
EPC and SRI

Key impacts

Results of CBA and environmental and social impact assessment in relation to the baseline are extrapolated to the EU level (for EU population 2025-2050)

	Austria	Croatia	Greece	Hungary	Italy	Poland	Slovenia	EU potential (for 450 mio citizens)	
Cost-Benefit analysis	Sum of Costs (million EUR)	1,582.5	120.3	790.8	7,123.1	2,503.0	2,009.0	19.7	77,213
	Sum of Benefits (million EUR)	3,445.1	168.6	4,124.5	19,181.2	6,683.4	4,022.0	42.1	207,195
	Total CBA (million EUR)	1,862.2	48.2	3,333.6	12,058.0	4,179.0	1789.0	22.4	129,978
Environmental	Avoided GHG emissions (tons CO ₂ e)	358,111.0	89053.0	833,532.0	8,820,466.0	1,141,693.0	2,267,891.0	9,383.0	80,100,742
	Energy savings (GWh)	3,957.1	365.5	4,063.0	27,971.2	7,560.0	6,244.3	70.3	285,665
Social	Avg No. of jobs created by 2050	76,099.0	633.0	78,135.0	10,758.0	5,815.0	4,083.0	54.0	1,098,046

Roll-out pathways: summary

Energy Agencies planned the steps to enact the preferred Policy Option, with estimated timings for the implementation

Project achievements

Better Regulation Guideline

Energy Agencies applied methodology developed for EC

Data collection

Survey, interview, workshops
388 participants involved

Knowledge exchange

NextGenEPC cluster, SRI cluster

Survey and interview results are available

Journal Paper - published soon

Replicability to other MS

Practice collection, methodology guidance, policy measure tool available

Impact Assessment – access upon request

emp.onl/tunes

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Co-funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's funding instrument for the environment and climate action (LIFE programme) under grant agreement No 101120926.